

UZBEKISTAN IS MY COUNTRY

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AnDUPI, Ijtimoiy fanlarni o'qitish metodikasi kafedrasi o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada vatanga muhabbat, vatanparvarlik tuyg'usi kengroq yoritilgan bo'lib, yoshlarning yangi O'zbekistonni yanada taraqqiy etishiga qo'shgan hissasi haqida to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: vatan, mustaqillik, yangi O'zbekiston, Uchunchi Rennessans Homeland. What a precious word. When we hear this word, we understand the land where we were born and raised, the great school where we were educated, the family that grew up in the arms of our loved ones. It is a sacred place where man came into the world, took his first steps, and grew up. When you say the word "homeland", you feel love for the homeland. This feeling is called patriotism. Patriotism or national pride is a feeling of love, devotion and attachment to it. If you are heartbroken when you think of the house where you were born and grew up, if you gasp when you hear the word Uzbekistan, it means that one of these unique feelings - patriotism - is not alien to you. The feeling of love for the motherland is instilled in a person by the mother goddess, the teachings of the ancestors, the example of the father, the upbringing of the family, the education of teachers. It is through this feeling that one seeks to know the people around you, the essence of things. A sense of patriotism strengthens a person in difficult times, encourages him to honor his people, to be faithful to the traditions of their ancestors.

New Uzbekistan - in a new guise. Indeed, as a result of extensive reforms in our country, the beauty of our country is being added. That the dreams and hopes of our youth are being realized We apologize for living in such a peaceful and prosperous country not an exaggeration, I think. Speaking of peace, it is clear that reaching this level has not been easy. We know from history that there were hundreds and thousands of heroes in our homeland, and we all know their courage and bravery.

Indeed, we have no right to forget the sufferings of our people in the recent past, the tragic days when our destiny was on the brink. There is no future for a nation that does not know its history and forgets its past. It should be noted that the first cornerstone of our independence was laid by Islam Karimov Abduganievich. On August 31, 1991, at the sixth session of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, Uzbekistan declared the independence of Uzbekistan. Most importantly, in his speech, he said that "the policy of the independent state of Uzbekistan is based on the principles of humanity and goodness."

Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev officially accepted the post of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 14, 2016 at a joint session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan together with the confidence of our people in the good work initiated by Islam Karimov.

To further increase the effectiveness of ongoing reforms, to create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, modernization and liberalization of all spheres of life in order to implement the priorities for 2017-2021 Five priorities for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan has opened up a wide range of opportunities for our youth through the implementation of the Action Strategy for. Presidential Schools, Presidential University, Presidential Grant and President scholarships, Youth Forum, Young Scientist and many more The introduction of opportunities we young people to further explore, read worthy of study and for the great future of our country created a great opportunity for us to contribute.

To strengthen the sense of responsibility and responsibility for the fate and future of our country in the hearts of the younger generation, to ensure their active participation in the creative work to build a new Uzbekistan, to lay the foundations of the Third Renaissance, to increase their curiosity and responsibility in their chosen field. One of the main goals of the New Uzbekistan is to develop a sense of creativity, as well as the activities of talented young people, to make their achievements an example for all young people in our country. For this, everyone living in our country must have a high level of education, be enlightened and highly spiritual. The opportunity to see such wonderful days is the result of centuries-old dreams of our people, the efforts of our brave and courageous ancestors who fought against the enemies of our Motherland. In addition, President Sh. Mirziyoyev's book "New Strategy" reads: "Today, the dreams and aspirations of our people, formed on the basis of our national thinking from the distant past to the present, reflected in various ideas and practical actions, are summed up in the concept of New Uzbekistan. . " [1] Indeed, living in a prosperous life today is not just a one-man show, but an effort to discover such a sunny country, despite the complex, difficult times that many people have experienced over the centuries as a result of their love for their homeland. as a result of his zeal, of course. First of all, in the phrase "New Uzbekistan" we mean putting the interests of the people above all else. In the new Uzbekistan, there will be kindness, respect for the elder, respect for the younger, mutual friendship, helping each other. It is up to us, the youth, to develop this country. Because we will be an example to the next generation by

contributing to the development of our new Uzbekistan with our work. That way, they can follow in our footsteps. This indicates the sustainable development of our new Uzbekistan, the presence of innovations. Along the way, it should be noted that large-scale reforms and innovations are being carried out throughout the country, competition is growing, and a society based on modern ideas is being built to achieve such lofty goals. Also, all of these reforms are focused on man, his life, rights and freedoms, dignity, needs and interests. So why don't we, the youth, live in such a dear country and contribute to its further development? Of course, if we do not try to make a small contribution while living in such a sacred place, it is considered that we have eaten the salt of our Motherland and spit on it. If our country has produced many scientists who have contributed to the development of the country, then there are those who do not make a small effort, even if we can not be like them? Our scholars and ancestors not only made world-class discoveries, but also made invaluable contributions to spreading the name of our country around the world. Because they added the name of their place of birth to their name so that the sense of homeland would help them in everything they do. Such names as Bukhari, Zamakhshari, Samarkandiy, Shoshiy, Tashkent, Fergani, Margnani, Khorezmi, Termez, Nasafiy appeared in this way. When we read the articles and poems of our ancestors, such as Behbudi, Fitrat, Qodiri, Cholpon, written with great sorrow, we feel how hard it is to stand on the soil of the Motherland and live with the pain of losing the Motherland.

The President outlined the tasks set for young people in creating an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan. All this, of course, for the further development of our country. So, if we, the youth, do not contribute to the further development of our new Uzbekistan, who will?

So, let's justify the sincere confidence of our President in the youth and use all our opportunities to make our new Uzbekistan more prosperous, to move forward among the developed countries, to build a new democratic society, to lay the foundation for the future. We feel and see our new Uzbekistan at every step, in the daily activities of our country. The future of Uzbekistan depends in many ways on the education of our youth and our development into a harmoniously developed generation. In this sense, we must feel the idea of national independence with our hearts and minds, love and study national values and history, and be faithful to them. We should be happy in a country called Uzbekistan, where gold blooms in the soil, spring whispers in winter, and nightingales can't finish singing the hymn every morning. As our elders said, we

should live with gratitude. The great representative of Uzbek literature, the Hero of Uzbekistan Ozod Sharafuddinov has the following thoughts: "Dear compatriot! We Uzbeks are proud of you. Today we are trying to be among the nations of the world. But no matter how high we are, no matter how low we are, no matter how low we are. We know that God created all His servants on the porch of the world as equals and friends. Yes, we are brothers to all nations, but we have no language barrier in front of anyone. So we have every reason to say, "Wherever I go, my head is twisted." Let there be no soul who has not heard the fame of the Uzbeks, who has not heard the definition of the heavenly country "Uzbekistan". " [2] Therefore, when we turn to Uzbekistan alone, let us stand tall for our demonic contribution to the development of this beautiful country. We were born and grew up in this dear Motherland. We feel it is our duty to love him and cherish him like the apple of our eye. Therefore, the development of the country depends on its children, every young generation living in it, their spiritual and physical maturity. This, in turn, encourages every citizen to feel a high sense of civic responsibility, to live in harmony with the interests of this country, this people. So, is it possible not to love the river of love, the land of truth ?!

List of used literature:

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2. New history of Uzbekistan. Book 2. Uzbekistan during the Soviet era. Tashkent: Sharq, 2000
3. <https://saviya.uz/ijod/publitsistika/olsam-ayrilmasman-quchaqlaringdan/>

